

THE INFLUENCE OF COMPENSATION, WORK ENVIRONMENT, AND EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION ON TEACHER JOB SATISFACTION**Aldo Syahril Muda Pratama¹, Agus Mulyono²**^{1,2,3} Universitas Maarif Hasyim Latif Sidoarjo

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Abstract: Teachers as human resources have a very important role in achieving the goals of educational institutions. Paying attention to teacher job satisfaction is an important step to improve the quality of education and ensure their welfare. Therefore, in-depth research is needed on the factors that influence teacher job satisfaction, as a basis for evaluating management policies and practices in educational institutions. This paper presents a study of the influence of compensation, work environment, and extrinsic motivation on teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation. This research is a type of quantitative research. The subjects in this research were teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation. The technique used in sampling was a saturated sampling technique with a total of 46 respondents. The method used in analyzing is multiple linear regression. The results of the research show that the compensation variable has a significant positive effect on teacher job satisfaction with a value of t count $6,077 > t$ -table $1,681952$, the work environment variable has a significant positive effect on teacher job satisfaction with a value of t count $2,653 > t$ -table $1,681952$, then the extrinsic motivation variable has a significant positive effect on teacher job satisfaction with a calculated t value $2,125 > t$ -table $1,681952$, while the variables of compensation, work environment, and extrinsic motivation simultaneously have a significant positive effect on teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation.

Keywords: Compensation, Work Environment, Extrinsic Motivation, and Job Satisfaction

This is an open-access article under the [CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) license**Introduction**

The Independent Learning Policy introduced by the Minister of Education and Culture Nadiem Makarim in 2020 has triggered various responses, in line with the vision and mission of creating superior and competitive human resources in various fields. Educational institutions must innovate and have competitiveness to avoid being left behind in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Surahman et al., 2022). Teachers play a crucial role as human resources in achieving the goals of educational institutions. Despite the importance of a superior curriculum, the role of teachers remains a key element in realizing this vision. Therefore, improving the quality of education in every institution must pay attention to teachers' job satisfaction, even though job satisfaction is essentially personal.

Job satisfaction can be defined as an individual's response to the condition or situation in which he works Sopiah Dalam (Pristiyanti, 2016). Job satisfaction is quite important because of

the great benefits for teachers and educational institutions. With high enthusiasm and motivation, satisfied teachers will work critically and responsibly, create a conducive work atmosphere, and have a good attendance rate. This increases productivity and reduces turnover, so that the goals of educational institutions can be achieved properly (Afriansyah et al., 2022).

One of the many causes that can affect job satisfaction is compensation. Ambar Sulistyani and Rosidah in (Suhendar, 2018) stated that compensation is all forms of compensation that employees receive for their contributions in carrying out their duties. Providing appropriate compensation, either in the form of money, allowances, or additional facilities, is an effective strategy to encourage teachers' active participation in their professional tasks (Kus Daru Widayati, 2018). Competitive compensation is essential to attract and retain qualified teachers, ensuring that educational institutions have competent and qualified teaching staff (Situmorang et al., 2022). However, the results of interviews with several teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation showed that there are aspects that need to be improved in the provision of compensation, especially related to social security. Teachers do not receive health and employment insurance benefits, which they consider essential to their well-being. This shortcoming not only has the potential to affect the foundation's image in the eyes of the public but also its attractiveness as a workplace for prospective new teachers. Therefore, improvements in the provision of compensation can be an important step to increase teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation.

In addition, there is another important element that can affect teachers' job satisfaction is the work environment. According to Andriany in (Dhani & Surya, 2023), the work environment includes facilities, equipment, atmosphere, and workplace conditions. In order for employees, including teachers, to work comfortably and productively, the organization is responsible for providing a comfortable and conducive work environment.

Research by Yugusna et al. in (Latifah & Nurmalasari, 2018) shows that the work environment is considered good if employees are able to work optimally and feel comfortable. A comfortable and safe environment makes employees more focused and enthusiastic at work, increasing productivity and quality of results. Conversely, a poor work environment can degrade employee conditions, leading to dissatisfaction and inefficient performance, which negatively impacts the achievement of organizational goals (Danisa, 2023).

Based on the results of the observations made, it was found that the office space and teacher room at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation for the three levels of education (KB, RA, and MI) are still combined into one, which causes various facilities such as desks, chairs, computers, and other equipment to be used interchangeably. This condition creates challenges for teachers' work effectiveness due to limited access to individually needed facilities. Teachers are expected to share these resources, which may reduce productivity and convenience when carrying out their tasks. A further impact of this suboptimal working condition is the potential for a decrease in teachers' satisfaction at work.

Meanwhile, teachers' job satisfaction can also be influenced by extrinsic motivational factors. This motivation comes from outside the individual and encourages the individual to work

optimally (Nofi et al., 2017). Organizations often use extrinsic motivation to stimulate and motivate employees, in the hope of increasing job satisfaction which can then have a positive impact on improving performance and achieving organizational goals.

According to an interview with a teacher at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation, it was identified that the lack of motivation from the school is a problem that needs attention. For example, teachers are expected to participate in various competitions without any guarantee of awards, even though these achievements have the potential to increase the school's positive image. This lack of appreciation or appreciation for teachers' achievements can reduce their enthusiasm and participation in school activities. Extrinsic motivation is very important in improving teachers' morale and the quality of education. Therefore, the management needs to increase extrinsic motivation as an effort to improve the quality and quality of education at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation.

The Roudlotul Jannah Foundation is a private educational foundation located at Jl. Masjid RT.04/RW.03 Kajartengguli, Prambon District, Sidoarjo Regency, East Java. This foundation combines the curriculum of the Ministry of Religion and the Ministry of Education and Culture flexibly, as well as adopting the Cambridge curriculum. The Cambridge curriculum is one part of the bilingual classroom, where learning is bilingual, from the delivery of material to assessment. To achieve organizational goals, educational institutions must strive to meet the needs of educators, both from basic aspects to higher levels. This aims to create job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation can continue to be improved.

With the existing background, this study aims to determine the impact of these three variables on teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Prambon Education Foundation, Sidoarjo.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

According to Suwanto and Prisa (2018), Human Resource Management is part of general administration which includes planning, organizing, directing, and controlling activities related to human resources. The aspects included include recruitment, training, development, and evaluation of employee performance. Effective HR management is key to achieving the overall goals of the organization, as it ensures that every individual in the organization works optimally.

Compensation

Simamora's opinion in (Agustin et al., 2023) It is a reward received by employees for their contributions to the organization which is divided into two types, namely directly including incentives, salaries, wages while indirectly covering benefits.

Work Environment

Enny's opinion in (Dhani & Surya, 2023) The work environment can be defined as an environment where employees work in which there are elements where the employee works. For example, the cleanliness of the work environment, the completeness of equipment and so on.

Extrinsic Motivation

Suhardi's opinion in (Basri et al., 2023) Extrinsic motivation is a motivation that arises due to the influence of the external environment that requires a cause that makes a person inspired from not trying to do something. For example, in the form of awards, compliments, positions, money, bonuses, incentives, gifts, large salaries, and so on.

Job Satisfaction

Sopiah's opinion in (Pristiyanti, 2016), what is meant by job satisfaction is an individual's response to the conditions or situations in which he works. The response describes a sense of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Job satisfaction is most easily felt by employees after workers compare what they get from their work results and it turns out that it is not in accordance with what they expect.

Saripuddin's opinion in (Azhar et al., 2020) Job satisfaction is a tendency when showing the level of happiness or feelings felt by workers from the way they see and complete work in their activities related to work conditions, relationships between workers, and rewards obtained from work.

Meanwhile, according to Umar in (Mardiana, 2016) job satisfaction is an individual's emotion or evaluation of work related to the environment in which he works, whether the job can meet his desires and expectations and needs.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that compensation has a significant positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation

H2: It is suspected that the Work Environment has a significant positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation

H3: It is suspected that extrinsic motivation has a significant positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation

H4: It is suspected that Compensation, Work Environment, and Extrinsic Motivation have a significant positive effect on teachers' job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation simultaneously

Methods

This research was carried out at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation which is located on Jl. Masjid, RT.04/RW.03, Kajartengguli Village, Prambon District, Sidoarjo Regency, East Java. This foundation is known as one of the educational institutions that is highly committed to improving the quality of education in its region. The quantitative approach is the method chosen for this research, the goal is to measure and analyze the data numerically to obtain objective and generalizable results.

In this study, there is a population consisting of 46 teachers who teach at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation. The population consists of 36 Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (MI) teachers, 7 Raudlatul Athfal (RA) teachers, and 3 Play Group (KB) teachers. The data on the number of teachers has been verified by the foundation to ensure the accuracy of the information.

The saturated sampling technique was used as a sampling method with a small population of 46 teachers, where the entire population was used as a research sample.

Questionnaires using the Likert scale are the main instruments for data collection. The Likert Scale measures respondents' perceptions, attitudes, and opinions towards various statements in the questionnaire, allowing for structured and easy-to-analyze data.

To analyze the data, "multiple linear regression" is the technique chosen in this study. This technique was chosen because it can identify and measure the contribution of any independent variable to the dependent variable, which can then be used in drawing conclusions and providing recommendations based on the findings of the research.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	<i>N</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>
(X1)	46	4	20	14.20	2.526
(X2)	46	5	15	10.91	1.964
(X3)	46	6	15	11.22	2.139
(Y)	46	10	24	17.76	2.718

Source: Research Results (2024)

- The test presented in table 1 provides a fairly comprehensive overview of the compensation variable (X1). It can be seen from the data that this variable has a value range ranging from a minimum of 4 to a maximum of 20. This variable has an average value of 14.20 which is the midpoint of the value range. The compensation variable shows a standard deviation of 2.526, which indicates that most of the data distribution values are within the approximate range of 2.526 from the mean value. In addition, if the mean value exceeds the standard deviation ($14.20 > 2.526$), it means that the distribution of data on the compensation variable (X1) is good and homogeneous throughout the research period.
- The examination presented in Table 1 provides a fairly comprehensive overview of the work environment variables (X2). It can be seen from the data that this variable has a value range ranging from a minimum of 5 to a maximum of 15. The average is 10.91 which is the midpoint of the value range. The work environment variable showed a standard deviation of 1.964, which indicates that most of the work environment values are within the estimated range of 1.964 from the average value. With a standard

- deviation of 1.964 which is relatively small compared to the average, it indicates that the X2 data has a good data distribution and is homogeneous throughout the research period.
- c) The examination presented in table 1 provides a fairly comprehensive overview of extrinsic motivation variables (X3). From this information, it can be seen that the minimum value of the X3 variable data is 6 and the maximum value is 15. The average value of 11.22 indicates the center of the data distribution. With a standard deviation of 2.139 which is relatively small compared to the average, it indicates that the X3 data has a good data distribution and is homogeneous throughout the research period.
- d) Furthermore, the examination presented in table 1 provides a fairly comprehensive overview of the job satisfaction variable (Y). From this information, it can be seen that the minimum value of the Y variable data is 10 and the maximum value is 24. The average value of 17.76 indicates the center of the data distribution. With a standard deviation of 2.718 which is relatively small compared to the average, it indicates that the Y data has a good data distribution and is homogeneous throughout the research period.

Validity Test

A questionnaire is considered valid when its statement effectively reflects what the questionnaire is intended to measure. If each item in each indicator yields a significant value (< 0.05), it indicates the validity of the questionnaire and qualifies as a reliable research tool.

Table 2. Validity Test Results

Variable	<i>r-count</i>	<i>R-table</i>	<i>Mr.</i>	<i>Ket.</i>	
X1	X1_1	.811**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X1_2	.757**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X1_3	.805**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X1_4	.826**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
X2	X2_1	.772**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X2_2	.790**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X2_3	.822**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
X3	X3_1	.848**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X3_2	.812**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	X3_3	.799**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
And	Y_1	.657**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	Y_2	.701**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	Y_3	.626**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	Y_4	.740**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>
	Y_5	.514**	0.2455	0.000	<i>Valid</i>

Source: Research Results (2024)

The results of this study show that all questionnaire statement items of the four variables have r-count numbers exceeding the r-table numbers, which indicates that the entire data is valid.

Reliability Test

The opinion of Sugiyono (2016) is that if the measurement is carried out again with the same instrument and object, the results will not change. A questionnaire is declared reliable if an individual's answer to the questionnaire statement is stable or consistent over time or results in a Cronbach Alpha number of >0.60 .

Table 3. Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's	Cronbach's	Ket.
	Alpha	Alpha hinted at	
X1	0.812	0.60	Reliable
X2	0.707	0.60	Reliable
X3	0.750	0.60	Reliable
And	0.655	0.60	Reliable

Source: Research Results (2024)

The results of this study show that all questionnaire statement items from the four variables have a Cronbach Alpha number of >0.60 which indicates that the entire data is declared reliable.

Table 4. Normality Test Results

No.	Nilai Asym. Sig	The value of sig. Designated
1	0,200	$>0,05$

Source: Research Results (2024)

Kolmogorov-Smirnov is a versatile non-parametric test, sensitive to distribution variance, and can be applied to a wide range of distributions. The K-S test was chosen as a useful instrument to evaluate the application of data distribution in statistical analysis. The data is considered normally distributed if the value of Asymptotic Significance (Asym. Sig) more than 0.05 so that it does not cause the rejection of the null hypothesis. It can be seen that the value generated from this test is 0.200, so the data is normally distributed because it is more than 0.05.

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	BRIGHT

1	X1	0.656	1.525
2	X2	0.758	1.32
3	X3	0.790	1.266

Source: Research Results (2024)

In this study, the resulting values met the criteria that showed that there was no strong indication of the multicollinearity problem between variables. This can be seen from the tolerance value produced exceeding the value of 0.10 and the VIF number shows a result of less than 10.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2. Scatterplot

To test heteroscedasticity, the researchers used a scatter plot graph to check if there was a clear pattern in the residual spread along the Y-axis. This illustrates that there is no strong evidence to support the existence of heteroscedasticity in the data.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Tabel 6. Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		t	Mr.
		B	Std. Error		
1 (Constant)	2.172	1.548		1.403	0.168
X1	0.646	0.106	0.601	6.077	0.000
X2	0.338	0.127	0.244	2.653	0.011
X3	0.243	0.114	0.191	2.125	0.039

Source: Source: Research Results (2024)

The result of the equation:

$$Y = 2,172 + 0,646X1 + 0,338X2 + 0,243X3 + e$$

- a) A positive sign of a constant coefficient of 2.172 indicates that job satisfaction will increase by 2.172 if all independent variables are considered constant or zero. These results show that the constant in question contributes an additional factor to job satisfaction that is not taken into account by other independent variables. The constant coefficient also serves as an indicator of the collective impact of the three independent variables on job satisfaction. This means that an increase of one unit in the three independent variables will result in an increase in job satisfaction by 2,172 units.
- b) A positive value of 0.646 on the regression coefficient of variable X1 (compensation) indicates that, assuming all other independent variables in the constant model, each unit increase in variable X1 (compensation) will increase variable Y (job satisfaction) by 0.646, and vice versa.
- c) A positive value of 0.338 on the regression coefficient of variable X2 (work environment) indicates that, assuming all other independent variables in the constant model, each increase of one unit in variable X2 (work environment) will increase the variable Y (job satisfaction) by 0.338, and vice versa.
- d) A positive value of 0.243 on the regression coefficient of variable X3 (extrinsic motivation) indicates that, assuming all other independent variables in the constant model, each unit increase in variable X3 (extrinsic motivation) will increase the variable Y (job satisfaction) by 0.243, and vice versa.

Partial Test (t-Test)

- 1) In the first hypothesis test (H1), the t-value of the X1 variable (compensation) determined based on the analysis in table 6 is 6.077. The information presented illustrates that t-counts are more than t-tables ($6.077 > 1.681952$), with a p-value of 0.000 less than 0.05. Therefore, it was stated that it rejected H0 and accepted Ha, so it was concluded that the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation was positively and significantly influenced by the compensation variable.
- 2) In the second hypothesis test (H2), the t-value of the X2 variable (work environment) determined based on the analysis in table 6 is 2.653. The information presented illustrates that the t-calculated value is more than the t-table ($2.653 > 1.681952$), with a p-value of 0.011 less than 0.05. Therefore, it was stated that they rejected H0 and accepted Ha, so it was concluded that the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation was positively and significantly influenced by the variables of the work environment.
- 3) In the third hypothesis test (H3), the t-value of the X3 variable (extrinsic motivation) determined based on the analysis in table 6 is 2.125. The information presented illustrates that t-count is more than t-table ($2.125 > 1.681952$), with a p-value of 0.039 less than 0.05. Therefore, it was declared to reject H0 and accept Ha, so it was concluded that the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Education

Foundation was positively and significantly influenced by extrinsic motivation variables.

Table 7. Simultaneous Test Results (Test F)

Model	F Calculate	Sig.	F Table	Sig. Stipulated
1	38.012	.000b	2,83	< 0.05

Source: Research Results (2024)

- 4) In the fourth hypothesis test (H4), the F value calculated based on the analysis was 38.012. The information presented illustrates that F counts more than F table ($38.012 > 2.83$), with a p-value of 0.000 less than 0.05. Therefore, it was stated that it rejected H0 and accepted Ha, so it was concluded that teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Education Foundation was influenced together by the three independent variables that existed positively and significantly.

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Type	R	R Square
1	.855a	0.731

Source: Research Results (2024)

The determination coefficient (R^2) of 0.731 was obtained from data analysis using SPSS. The information presented illustrates that the three variables together explain 73.1% variation in job satisfaction (Y). Other factors that were not studied affected the remaining 26.9%.

The Effect of Compensation on Job Satisfaction

The partial test was carried out, resulting in a higher t-count value than the t-table ($6.077 > 1.681952$). In addition, a significance figure of 0.000 lower than 0.05 illustrates the hypothesis (H1) is acceptable. This shows that teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation can be positively affected by compensation significantly.

This finding is in line with Wibowo's statement (2016), that an organization's compensation system has a great influence on employee satisfaction at work. This means that the approach applied by organizations when determining employee compensation has the potential to have a direct impact on the level of employee satisfaction. This finding is in line with previous research by Jipi Listari and Khairul Bahrin (2021), which showed that compensation has a significant and positive impact on the job satisfaction of employees of PT. Ciptamas Bumi Harmonis.

The Influence of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction

The partial test was carried out, resulting in a higher t-count value than the t-table ($2.653 > 1.681952$). In addition, a significance figure of 0.011 lower than 0.05 illustrates the hypothesis (H1) is acceptable. This shows that the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation can be positively and significantly affected by the work environment.

This finding is in line with Anas' view (Nurlaela & Trianasari, 2021), revealing that the existence of a safe and comfortable work environment, starting from a physical or non-physical perspective, is very important for employees. This is believed to be a key factor in supporting employees to work optimally. Conversely, insecurity and discomfort in the work environment, both physical and non-physical, have the potential to reduce the level of employee satisfaction at work. This finding is also in line with previous research by Ikhlas Burhan, Abdi Akbar, and Agung Widhi Kurniawan (2022), that the work environment has a significant and positive impact on employee job satisfaction at PT. Bantimurung Indah Maros Regency.

The Effect of Extrinsic Motivation on Job Satisfaction

The partial test was carried out, resulting in a higher t-count value than the t-table ($2.125 > 1.681952$). In addition, a significance figure of 0.039 which is lower than 0.05 illustrates the hypothesis (H1) is acceptable. This shows that the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation can be positively and significantly influenced by extrinsic motivation.

This finding is in line with the view of Winardi Dalam (Chandra Wibisono, 2022) who states that motivation has a strong relationship with human resources, because motivation is an important factor needed by employees to complete their tasks well. When employees have a high level of extrinsic motivation, they tend to work better and contribute optimally to the achievement of organizational goals so that there is a sense of satisfaction from employees who carry out their duties. This finding is in line with previous research by Anggoro Wisnu Aji, and Jajuk Herawati (2022), the study shows that extrinsic motivation has a significant and positive influence on the job satisfaction of employees of Toko Pamella 6 Supermarket Yogyakarta.

The Effect of Compensation, Work Environment, and Extrinsic Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Simultaneous testing was carried out, resulting in a higher F-count value than the F-table ($38.012 > 2.83$). In addition, a significance figure of 0.000 lower than 0.05 illustrates the hypothesis (H4) is acceptable. This shows that teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation can be jointly affected by compensation, work environment, and extrinsic motivation positively and significantly.

The results of this study show that compensation is one of several important aspects that support teacher job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation. It can be seen that teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation have the assumption that competitive compensation provides job satisfaction, because they believe that a contribution and effort made must be proportional to the reward they receive.

In addition, the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation is also supported by one of the important factors, namely the work environment. It can be seen that teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation have the assumption that a safe and comfortable work environment is able to create a more positive atmosphere, thus allowing them to give their best in the learning process.

Meanwhile, the job satisfaction of teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation is also supported by one of the other important factors, namely extrinsic motivation. It can be seen that teachers at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation have the assumption that awards for work achievements have an important meaning. Various forms of rewards, such as verbal praise, written awards, and material rewards, can provide personal satisfaction that encourages high morale for teachers.

Conclusion

Teachers' job satisfaction at the Roudlotul Jannah Foundation is significantly and positively influenced by Compensation, Work Environment, and Extrinsic Motivation. The results of the analysis showed that each of these variables had a significant positive impact on Job Satisfaction. Simultaneously, these three variables also contribute significantly to increasing the job satisfaction of the foundation's teachers. This indicates that in order to improve teachers' job satisfaction, attention should be paid not only to the compensation received, but also to the conditions of the work environment and extrinsic motivation given to teachers.

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